

Khafre's pyramid and Saturn's rings

The Giza planetary correlation, extended.

Ian Douglas, Neferneferuamun, Nana

ian@zti.co.za

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8452-7111>

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Abstract

The Giza Big Dipper correlation hypothesis shows that there were six main pyramids at Giza. In turn, these six pyramids correspond to the first six planets, with Khafre corresponding to Saturn, as shown in *The six pyramids and planets at Giza*.

The Italian researchers, Maragioglio & Rinaldi (M&R), pointed out evidence for what they considered to be the originally planned base for Khafre's pyramid, 60 cubits bigger than the current base. In this paper, I show how M&R's proposed original dimensions should instead be taken as the base of a "virtual" pyramid, along with two other "virtual pyramids" suggested by the enclosure features. These three virtual pyramids then slot in perfectly to the Pyramids and Planets correlation, giving us the diameters of Saturn's main rings and the Cassini Gap.

Keywords: Egyptology, Giza, History of Science, History of Astronomy.

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1 Introduction

In *Zep Tepi Mathematics 101* [1], we presented a correlation between the Big Dipper and nearby stars, and the original Giza site plan, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 2 shows a 3D view. The plan has the three existing pyramids and three which have been demolished. One of these was documented by Frederich Norden (*Voyage d'Égypte et de Nubie* [2], Figure 3), and it is possible that Pococke (*A description of the East, and some other countries ...* [3]) documented the same one, plus one more. Figure 5 shows Pococke's sketch of the pyramids, and Figure 6 shows the 3D CAD rendering rotated to match Pococke's sketch.

The missing pyramid (P5), shown in red behind Khafre, was probably demolished during dynastic times, and some of the casing stones reused for Menkaure's pyramid, since the base sizes and height, and thus the slopes, of the two pyramids were very similar.

Figure 1: The site map showing the Big Dipper correlation.

Figure 2: A 3D CAD view of the site.

Figure 3: Norden's four pyramids.

Figure 4: Matching view for Norden's four pyramids. Note that his perspective is foreshortened and horizontally expanded.

Figure 5: Pococke's five pyramids.

Figure 6: 3D CAD view of site, rotated to match Pococke's drawing.

In *The six pyramids and planets at Giza* [4], I showed how the six pyramids also correspond to the first six planets, via a simple mapping:

Volume as a percentage of Khufu \implies Diameter as a percentage of Jupiter (142984 km)

The correlation is shown in Table 1.

We can label each pyramid with the corresponding planet, as shown in Figure 7.

Table 1: Pyramids and planets

Planet / Pyramid	Jupiter %	Khufu %	Px	Name	x	y	h
Jupiter / Khufu	100.00	100.00	P1	Khufu	440	440	280
Saturn / Khafre	84.30	85.38	P2	Khafre	411	411	274
Earth / Menkaure	8.92	8.97	P3	Menkaure	201	195	124
Venus / Thuban	8.47	8.47	P5	Thuban	193	200	119
Mars / Arcturus	4.75	4.75	P4	Arcturus	149	151	114.6
Mercury / Vega	3.41	3.41	P6	Vega	157	157	75

Figure 7: The site map showing pyramids and planets.

Note that the pyramids are arranged from left to right in corresponding planet size order, from smallest to largest.

2 The virtual pyramids

2.1 The first virtual pyramid

In their 1966 publication, *L'architettura delle piramidi menfite Testo 5.1*, with the diagrams in volume 5.2, authors Maragioglio and Rinaldi (M&R) discuss the idea that Khafre's pyramid was originally intended to have a base of 470 (royal) cubits (G), this being 60 G larger than the then-accepted 410 G base. They added markers for three of these corners to their diagram, with the fourth corner being the same as the existing south-west corner. I have highlighted these three points with red arrows in Figure 8, borrowed from their book. Note that both volumes are available on Archive.org, but their file name lengths break Zotero BibLaTeX functionality.

M&R write, *“The connection between the two foreparts might also have been made afterwards: they would therefore have been only the constructed part of the projected base platform of a pyramid that was intended to be much larger (470 cubits square) than it later became (410 cubits). It should be noted that the foreparts are of a size that the platform as originally planned could have supported both the pyramid of 470 cubits and a surrounding courtyard of 20 cubits as well as the relative enclosure wall.”*

Given that the difference is 60 G, if we add 60 to the currently accepted size of 411 G, then we get 471 G. Both 411 and 471 produce integer values for the heights based on the Pythagorean 3:4:5 design, so I would argue that these are the correct figures to work with.

M&R converted metres to cubits at 0.5250 m/G rather than 0.5236 m/G. If you use 0.5236, then you get 411 G and 471 G rounded from their metre measurements.

A pyramid with a 471 G square base, and the same slope as Khafre, would have a height of 314 G. This value of 100π acts as confirmation that 471 G is the correct value to work with, since π is very much the

Figure 8: M&R's diagram with extra corners noted.

designer's signature.

Note that the 60 ϵ size difference is 31.416 metres, again referencing π . Also, each side slope is 392.5 ϵ , and the sum of the four side slopes is $4 \times 392.5 = 1570 \epsilon$, or 500×3.14 . Similarly, the perimeter minus the height is $4 \times 471 - 314 = 1570$, again.

I have drawn the base and side view of this virtual pyramid in red, along with Khafre's base and side in black, in Figure 9. Note that M&R's diagram is incorrectly drawn, with the north-south distance shorter than the east-west distance. My coloured squares are correct. You can confirm this by measuring on Figure 8.

Figure 9: Actual and first virtual bases, plan and side views. Scales are different.

We now perform the same volume-to-diameter transformation used in *The six pyramids and planets at Giza* [4], on the M&R virtual pyramid, as shown in Table 2.

These diameters are illustrated on a diagram of Saturn with the A and B rings, which are visible from Earth, separated by the Cassini gap, in Figure 10. The black diameter is from Khafre's pyramid, and the red from M&R's virtual pyramid.

Table 2: Volumes to diameters I

Pyramid	Base side	Height	Volume C^3	% Khufu	⇒ Diameter km
Khafre	411	274	15,428,118	85.38	122,083
M&R virtual	471	314	23,219,358	128.50	183,737

Figure 10: Mapping Khafre and M&R to Saturn.

2.2 The second virtual pyramid

We note that the walls to the east of the pyramid, and the cutting to the west, leave space for another virtual pyramid, with a base 537 C square, and a height of 358 C , again with the same slope as Khafre. This is illustrated in Figure 11, in blue.

Figure 11: The second virtual pyramid, plan and side views. Scales are different.

Table 3 shows the mapping from this virtual pyramid to a diameter.

Table 3: Volumes to diameters II

Pyramid	Base side	Height	Volume C^3	% Khufu	⇒ Diameter km
Khafre	411	274	15,428,118	85.38	122,083
M&R virtual	471	314	23,219,358	128.50	183,737
Second virtual	537	358	34,412,034	190.44	272,299

We add this diameter to our diagram of Saturn in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Mapping the second virtual pyramid to Saturn.

2.3 The third virtual pyramid

We now construct a third virtual pyramid, so that it is partly composed of M&R's pyramid, and partly of the second virtual pyramid. The south west corner aligns with that of the second virtual pyramid, and the north east corner aligns with M&R's virtual pyramid. The base is then 513 ƒ square, and the height 342 ƒ, again with the same slope as Khafre. This is illustrated in Figure 13, in green.

Figure 13: The third virtual pyramid, plan and side views. Scales are different.

Table 4 shows the mapping of this third virtual pyramid to a diameter.

Table 4: Volumes to diameters III

Pyramid	Base side	Height	Volume ƒ ³	% Khufu	⇒ Diameter km
Khafre	411	274	15,428,118	85.38	122,083
M&R virtual	471	314	23,219,358	128.50	183,737
Second virtual	537	358	34,412,034	190.44	272,299
Third virtual	513	342	30,001,266	166.03	237,396

We add this diameter to our diagram of Saturn in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Mapping all three virtual pyramids to Saturn.

3 Comparing the results

We can now numerically correlate the implied diameters from the virtual pyramids, to Saturn's main rings, visible from Earth. Note that it is difficult to detect the exact edges of these rings, since the constituent material is sparse and relatively small. The rings are rebuilt from collisions, and cleaned by Saturn's moons, so they change dynamically over time.

In terms of the Giza Big Dipper stellar alignment, Giza was built around 55.5k BCE, so the rings would have been a little different back then.

The Cassini Gap is part of both the outer A and inner B rings, and in the same way, the green virtual pyramid is part of both the red and blue virtual pyramids.

Table 5: Comparing the actual diameters to modelled diameters

Item	Diameter km	Pyramid correlated	⇒ diameter km	Accuracy %
Saturn	120,536	Khafre	122,083	101.28
Inner edge of B ring	184,000	M&R virtual	183,737	99.86
Average of Cassini Division	239,750	Third virtual	237,396	99.02
Outer edge of A ring	273,550	Second virtual	272,299	99.54

4 Conclusion

Through the use of one definitely-indicated virtual pyramid, and two deduced ones, we get an excellent correlation between Khafre's pyramid and immediate enclosure, and Saturn's rings.

It is possible to size the second (blue) base more exactly, but that produces a pyramid with a non-integer height.

The formula is $base = \sqrt[3]{\frac{diameter}{142984} \times 440^2 \times 280 \times \frac{3}{2}}$

So for example, for a diameter matching the A ring's outer edge of 237,550 km, we would need a base of 537.817 G. The closest integer is 538, but that produces a height of 358.67 G. 537 G is the closest that produces an integer height. The size of the second base affects the size of the third.

If Khafre's base was 409.26, the Khafre — Saturn correlation would be almost perfect, but a base of 409 does not have an integer height. It would need to be either 408 or 411, and they chose 411 because that number provides various other functions. See, for example *Khafre's pyramid elegantly encodes the speed of light* [5], *The Consequences of Legon's Rectangle: The Rational Giza Design* [6], and *The Douglas Triangle, Khufu and Khafre* [7].

If the builders intended to reference Saturn's rings in this manner, then we need to ask how they were able to accurately measure the diameters. In more recent times, Galileo Galilei was the first to observe the rings of Saturn in 1610, but did not identify them as rings because his telescope was underpowered.

Christiaan Huygens identified them as rings in 1655, and in 1675, Giovanni Cassini observed that the main rings had gaps between them, with the largest of these later named in his honour.

If our model of the pyramids and planets is correct, and extensible to Saturn's rings as discussed here, then whoever built Giza was at least as advanced as 17th century Europe. I am busy with another paper about the Bent Pyramid, which will include showing how the pyramids and planets model is continued at Dahshur. The Bent pyramid does both Uranus and Neptune. That would put the builders at least at the same level of development as 1846 when Johann Galle spotted Neptune.

5 Bibliography

For Maragioglio & Rinaldi's books, see: <https://archive.org/search?query=Maragioglio+%26+Rinaldi>

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